

Direct Growth of Rectangular 2D Layered Metal-Halide Perovskite Microcrystal Photonic Cavities on Functional Substrates

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Abstract. Two-dimensional layered perovskites (2DLPs) are emerging as versatile semiconductors for optoelectronic and photonic applications thanks to their intrinsic electronic confinement, high excitonic binding energy, and large compositional tunability. However, most fabrication methods yield either grainy 2D perovskite films, microcrystal powders, or microcrystals with highly irregular shapes. Here, we present a rapid and tunable recrystallization-based approach to fabricate single-crystalline 2DLP microcrystals with lateral dimensions from few to hundreds of microns, rectangular shape and excellent thickness homogeneity, and show how lateral size and thickness can be adjusted by the synthesis parameters. Our method involves dissolving 2DLP powders in a solvent–antisolvent mixture carefully tuned close to saturation, followed by crystallization controlled via a mild thermal gradient and solvent evaporation. Our protocol enables the straightforward synthesis of 2DLPs of diverse compositions and on a variety of substrates. Thanks to their regular shape, extremely flat surface and uniform thickness, our microcrystals show homogeneous emission over their entire surface, and behave as photonic cavities, sustaining confined modes and exciton-

polaritons. Such advantageous properties, which in the future could be combined with size and position control, have the potential to boost the development of optoelectronic microdevices, where the single crystals are implemented as emitting or sensing pixels.

1. Introduction

Two-dimensional layered perovskites (2DLPs) have emerged as a promising class of semiconductors for applications in optoelectronics and photonics.¹⁻³ Thanks to their hybrid structure that alternates layers of semiconducting PbX_6 octahedra and organic cations,⁴ these materials behave like intrinsic quantum wells.⁵ This anisotropic architecture leads to strong dielectric and quantum confinement in the vertical (out-of-plane) direction, and therefore to anisotropic carrier mobilities, high exciton binding energies, and strong and complex exciton-phonon coupling.⁶⁻¹¹ Their compositional tunability that comprises a vast range of organic molecules,¹² as well as different halides and metal cations, allowing for confinement and band alignment engineering makes them versatile materials that can be integrated in a large portfolio of devices, comprising application in solar cells,^{13, 14} light-emitting diodes (LEDs),^{15, 16} lasing,^{17, 18} sensing,¹⁹ and photonics.²⁰

Currently, the most common methods for synthesizing 2DLPs involve either a rapid precipitation from liquid precursors (e.g., by mixing metal halides in aqueous hydrohalic acids with amines),²¹⁻²⁴ or spin-coating polycrystalline thin films from solutions.^{25, 26} Thin films have been successfully integrated in solar cells,²⁷ LEDs,²⁸ and photodetectors,²⁹ however, for several applications single microcrystals with controlled shape can be more suitable. Ensembles or powders of 2DLP microcrystals can be fabricated by rapid precipitation methods, but mostly produce microcrystals with irregular morphology, from which single crystals can be obtained by exfoliation, but still feature irregular shapes and non-uniform thickness.²² Furthermore, such exfoliation is not upscalable and therefore not suitable for practical applications.

Limitations in crystal quality can be partially addressed using classical crystallization techniques like slow cooling³⁰ or vapor-based antisolvent diffusion.³¹ However, these methods are time consuming and typically yield large crystals (up to cm-size),³² which remain unsuitable for miniaturized applications. Consequently, there is a demand for protocols that can yield high-quality, size-tunable microcrystals with spatially homogeneous optoelectronic properties that are suitable for integration into single-microcrystal devices. Such microcrystals would also present an ideal platform for post-synthesis processing, such as the growth of electronic heterojunctions^{33, 34} or microfabrication to engineer metamaterials.

In this work, we present a fast, tunable, and reproducible protocol for fabricating rectangular, high-quality 2DLP microcrystals, with lateral sizes ranging from a few to hundreds of μm and homogeneous thickness in the submicron and micron range. Our method relies on the controlled recrystallization of 2DLP powders initially obtained through fast precipitation,²² which ensures the stoichiometric balance and purity of the final product. The 2DLP powders are dissolved in a solvent-antisolvent mixture, which is carefully balanced to drive the system close to saturation. The growth of microcrystals is then triggered and regulated via the combination of a mild thermal gradient and the progressive evaporation of the solvent, which over time increases both the antisolvent fraction and the material's concentration within the crystal growth environment. Our approach enables the growth of microcrystals with orthogonal edges, and minimal surface terracing, and therefore strongly reduces sources of defects. We use phenethylammonium lead bromide $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbBr}_4$ as case study to investigate the impact of growth parameters such as solvent/antisolvent ratio, temperature, and reaction volume on the crystal size and synthesis yield. We then demonstrate that our microcrystal fabrication approach can be extended to other organic cations and halide compositions, and that the microcrystals can be grown on various surfaces. To assess their optical properties, we compare the photoluminescence (PL) with that of corresponding powders and exfoliated microcrystal flakes, including decay times and PL quantum yield. Finally, we demonstrate that our regular microcrystals act as photonic cavities, sustaining confined optical modes, and we extract the refractive index dispersion from our reflectance data.

2. Results and Discussion

We first demonstrate our synthesis method with $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbBr}_4$ microcrystals (Figure 1a), and in later sections we introduce variations based on different halides and organic cations.

As a first step, $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbBr}_4$ powders were prepared by a previously developed antisolvent assisted fast crystallization technique,²² and then redissolved in acetonitrile (ACN).

Figure 1. Microcrystal growth via recrystallization demonstrated with $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbBr}_4$. A) Schematic representation of the recrystallization process: 2DLP powders obtained via rapid crystallization are dissolved in ACN, mixed with toluene acting as an antisolvent, heated, and drop-cast on a substrate. The gradual evaporation of ACN increases the material concentration and the antisolvent fraction, triggering the nucleation and growth of crystals. B,C) Optical microscopy images of an entire substrate (B) and at larger magnification (C) where the single crystals can be clearly resolved. D) Atomic-force microscopy (AFM) image of a section of a microcrystal evidencing the excellent thickness homogeneity. E) PL spectra of 5 individual microcrystals (grey) and their average spectrum (blue) compared with the PL spectrum of 2DLP powders obtained via rapid crystallization (green). F) Hyperspectral confocal photoluminescence (PL) maps of a single microcrystal (F) and corresponding 2DLP powder. The microcrystal shows uniform blue light emission (centered at 415 nm) across its entire surface, while the powder (G) displays different emission colors. The inset in (F) shows an optical image of the microcrystal. The spectral color scale bar in (G) is valid also for (F).

The recrystallization process that is at the core of our method relies on a careful adjustment of the 2DLP solubility in ACN, which is a good solvent for 2DLPs,³⁵ with an ACN-miscible antisolvent. The selected antisolvent must exhibit lower 2DLP solubility and, crucially, must

be less volatile than ACN. Based on these criteria, we chose toluene, which has a lower relative polarity (0.099 vs 0.46, with $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 1$)³⁶ and a lower vapor pressure (28.5 Torr vs 88.8 Torr) than ACN at room temperature. The interplay between temperatures and volatility of ACN and toluene plays an important role in controlling the crystal formation. ACN evaporates faster due to its higher volatility, creating a dynamic environment where the solute concentration gradually increases. As ACN evaporates, the remaining solvent, toluene, further drives the system toward supersaturation, facilitating the controlled growth of regularly shaped microcrystals.

For this case study, we use 2 mL of the stock solution in a standard vial, and add toluene in variable ratios. To increase the solubility of 2DLPs in the solvent mixture and to prevent sudden nucleation when the solution is dropped on the substrate, the solution is gently heated in a range of 25 – 80 °C (which is in between room temperature and the boiling point of ACN). Depending on the solvent/antisolvent ratio, the solution may initially appear cloudy, but should become clear during the heating step. We found that the minimum toluene/ACN ratio is ~0.4, below which full $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbBr}_4$ solubility cannot be achieved. The growth of microcrystals is triggered by drop-casting a drop of the solution (10-75 μl) on a 1 cm^2 substrate that is at a temperature of 25°C. The substrates are enclosed in a glass petri dish of known volume to maintain a controlled vapor environment. The growth process is defined by the evaporation time of the solvents lasts between 30 min and 2 h, depending on the specific conditions.

The resulting microcrystals are distributed on the surface of the substrate, usually with a higher concentration near the edges due to drop evaporation dynamics (Figure 1B).³⁷ A closer inspection reveals that microcrystals adopt a flat and well-defined, rectangular shape (Figure 1C-D), consistent with the layered structure of $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbBr}_4$. Confocal photoluminescence (PL) imaging (Figure 1F) reveals uniform emission in PL intensity, wavelength and line shape across the microcrystal surface. The structural and morphological homogeneity of the microcrystals is confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD, see Figure S1) and atomic force microscopy (AFM, see Figure 1D), which demonstrate that the sample contains only the expected $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbBr}_4$ phase and that microcrystals exhibit a flat surface over the entire microcrystal size. The PL emission exhibits a peak at 412 nm featuring a low-energy tail, consistent with our previous reports.^{22, 34, 38} PL spectra recorded from several microcrystals (Figure 1E) evidence perfect reproducibility of the PL spectral line shape and the higher color purity with respect to the emission of powders. A comparison with microcrystals obtained via rapid crystallization (Figures 1F-G) highlights the improved homogeneity for both morphology and spectral properties achieved with our recrystallization approach.

Figure 2. Correlation between synthesis parameters and microcrystal size and density. A) Schematic workflow of the image processing pipeline: substrate sampling, optical imaging, pixel classification, object identification, and sorting. B) Effect of solution temperature on the effective edge length of microcrystals, with representative optical microscope images of microcrystals. C) Influence of the antisolvent/solvent ratio on crystal size and morphology, with an inset showing microcrystals obtained below the critical ratio (red dashed line). D) Height distribution of the microcrystals obtained with the synthesis conditions indicated by the red arrows.

To investigate the tunability of our protocol in terms of fabricating microcrystals of different size, on different time scales, and with microcrystal yield, we identified four key parameters that significantly influence the recrystallization process: the solvent/antisolvent ratio, the temperature of the solution, the deposited drop volume, and the concentration of the stock solution. These factors control the crystallization dynamics by influencing the degree of

supersaturation, the solvent evaporation rate, and the total amount of material available for crystal growth.

The lateral size of the microcrystals, their height, and their density per cm² were selected as the primary observables to assess the growth, as these parameters provide insight into the crystallization dynamics, and are relevant for the envisioned purpose of the microcrystal fabrication. Size and density were quantified through a custom image processing workflow that combines the Ilastik neural network for pixel classification³⁹ with self-developed Python image analysis scripts for object recognition and size measurement (Figure 2a). For every growth condition, representative optical images across the substrate in x- and y-direction were evaluated to determine the lateral size distribution of the whole substrate (Figure S3).

Higher temperatures of the starting solution lead to larger lateral crystal size, as evident in Figure 2B, while increasing the solvent/antisolvent ratio tends to produce crystals with smaller edge lengths. This behavior can be interpreted in the context of classical nucleation theory. In this framework, the degree of supersaturation plays a critical role, as it dictates the free energy barrier for nucleation.⁴⁰ A higher antisolvent/solvent ratio rapidly drives the system into a highly supersaturated state by reducing the solubility of the solute, promoting the formation of numerous small nuclei that deplete available material and limit subsequent crystal growth.

On the other hand, lower ratios yield fewer nuclei and allow for the formation of larger crystals. The temperature of the solution further modulates the process: lower temperatures maintain a high degree of supersaturation, increasing nucleation rates and leading to smaller crystals, while higher temperatures reduce supersaturation, favoring growth over nucleation and resulting in larger lateral sizes. Since the substrate temperature was fixed at 25°C, evaporation dynamics were primarily influenced by the drop size. Shorter evaporation times due to smaller drops accelerate supersaturation, restrict growth time and yield smaller microcrystals (see Figure S4). Longer evaporation times (large drop deposition), by contrast, enable extended growth, resulting in larger lateral sizes.

The supersaturation of the solution, a key driver of nucleation, is influenced primarily by the antisolvent/solvent ratio (R) and the temperature of the deposited solution. Increasing the antisolvent/solvent ratio leads to higher supersaturation, which promotes the formation of more nucleation sites, resulting in a larger number of small microcrystals (Figure 2C). On the other hand, decreasing the antisolvent/solvent ratio reduces supersaturation, favoring the formation of fewer nuclei. Also the interplay between temperatures and volatility of ACN and toluene

plays an important role in controlling the crystal formation. ACN evaporates faster due to its higher volatility, creating a dynamic environment where the solute concentration gradually increases. As ACN evaporates, the remaining solvent, toluene, further drives the system toward supersaturation, facilitating the controlled growth of regularly shaped microcrystals. The height histograms in Figure 2D show that for smaller crystals the height is in the submicron range (panels (i) and (iv)), with a clear maxima at few hundred nanometers that correlate with the lateral size (that is for smaller crystals related to panel (i) the maximum is at lower values compared to larger crystals in panel (iv)). For large crystals (panels (ii) and (iii)) the height distribution is more spread out, and crystal thicknesses of few micrometer can occur (see Figure S4 for details on the height analysis).

Figure 3. Substrate compatibility and Mn doping of 2D layered perovskite microcrystals. (A–C) Optical images of 2DLP microcrystals with different composition: (A) BA_2PbBr_4 , (B)

fluorinated PEA-based perovskite (FPEA₂PbBr₄), and (C) PEA₂PbI₄. (D–F) Optical images of PEA₂PbBr₄ microcrystals deposited on various substrates: (D) APTES-functionalized SiO₂, (E) glass, and (F) silver-coated silicon. (G) Scheme of the synthesis process for Mn-doped PEA₂PbBr₄ microcrystals. (H) Optical microscope image of Mn-doped PEA₂PbBr₄ microcrystals, showing flat, rectangular morphology. (I) PL spectrum of a single Mn-doped microcrystal highlighting the emergence of a new emission band attributed to Mn²⁺ incorporation. Inset: magnified Mn-related emission band. (L) Confocal PL map of a single Mn-doped microcrystal.

Our fabrication method can be straightforwardly extended to other material compositions (different halides, and organic cations) as demonstrated in Figure 3 (A-C), yielding in all cases regular rectangular microcrystals with similar quality and yield as discussed for the PEA₂PbBr₄ case. Furthermore, the growth from drop deposition provides a great flexibility towards the substrates on which the microcrystals should be fabricated. Basically, the only requirements for substrates are that they are solvent resistant, and that they can stabilize an evaporating droplet. Figure 3d-f shows this flexibility with PEA₂PbBr₄ microcrystals fabricated on 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) functionalized SiO₂, glass, and silver.

To further demonstrate the versatility of our recrystallization protocol, we explored the incorporation of manganese(II) bromide (MnBr₂) as a dopant. A solution of MnBr₂ is mixed with a PEA₂PbBr₄ stock in acetonitrile, followed by the addition of toluene to induce recrystallization. The solution is heated and drop-cast on a substrate, where slow evaporation promotes the growth of isolated microcrystals. The resulting Mn-doped microcrystals exhibit a morphology comparable to the undoped counterparts, as seen in the optical microscopy image (Figure 3h). Notably, the photoluminescence (PL) spectrum of the doped crystals (Figure 3I) reveals the emergence of a broad red emission band, which is absent in the pristine material and typically attributed to Mn²⁺-related transitions. This red emission is further confirmed by confocal mapping (Figure 3L), highlighting the homogeneous distribution of the dopant within individual microcrystals. These results validate the adaptability of our recrystallization strategy to accommodate compositional tuning via post powder synthesis doping, while maintaining the high morphological quality and emission uniformity of the resulting microcrystals.

Figure 4. Optical properties. Photoluminescence spectra (A), decay traces collected at 410 nm (B), and quantum yield (C) of the microcrystals compared with their powder form and exfoliated flakes from powders ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=372$ nm). (D-F) Representative reflectance spectra recorded from $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbBr}_4$ (D) and PEA_2PbI_4 (E) microcrystals with different thickness that feature a series of minima due to Fabry-Perot resonances. The absorbance recorded from microcrystal ensembles is displayed by the grey-shaded curves. (F) Refractive index values extracted from the reflectance data using the displayed relation.

We assess the optical quality of the microcrystals by comparing their PL line shape, PL decay dynamics, and PL quantum yield (PLQY) with powder samples of corresponding composition, and with exfoliated flakes from such powders (Figure 4 A-C). Microcrystals and exfoliated flakes feature very similar PL spectra with a single emission peak that has a broader shoulder towards longer wavelength, while the powders show a second emission peak at lower wavelengths, in agreement with our previous works.^{11, 22, 34, 38} Interestingly, the microcrystals have a markedly faster PL decay with respect to the powders and exfoliated flakes, and we also observe significant differences in the PLQY of the three different samples. Here the powders have consistently lower PLQY compared to exfoliated flakes and ensembles of microcrystals,

which should stem from stronger reabsorption in the powder samples.⁴¹ Surprisingly, despite their more regular shape and thickness, the microcrystals show lower PLQY of 22% with respect to the exfoliated samples, for which have an average PLQY of 40%. We tentatively attribute this behavior to non-radiative recombination at the edges of the microcrystals, which would also explain the faster PL decay of the microcrystals in Figure 4B, since non-radiative recombination typically occurs on shorter time scales than radiative recombination.⁴² In this scenario larger crystals will have higher PLQY and longer PL life times since a smaller portion of the excitons will reach the crystal edges. This reasoning is in line with the larger lateral size and more irregular size and size distribution of exfoliated flakes (see Figure S6), which is reflected by the difference in spread of the PLQY values that we obtain from different regions of the same sample (see error bars in Figure 4C). Towards microcrystals with high PLQY, this behavior requires deeper investigation, and, for example, could stimulate the development of core-shell structures that separate the excitons from surface defects, as in the case for colloidal nanocrystals.⁴³

In addition to the rectangular lateral shape of the microcrystals, their top and bottom surfaces are extremely flat (see Figure 2D and Figure S2). Semiconductor microcrystal with such regular and homogeneous shape and high refractive index can function as open photonic cavities that sustain optical resonances (Fabry-Perot resonator). We have measured the reflectance from single $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbBr}_4$ and PEA_2PbI_4 microcrystal with different thickness, and observe a series of minima in reflectance that correspond to the optical cavity modes, with $\lambda_m = 2 n H/m$, where m is the mode order, H the height of the microcrystal, and n the refractive index of the perovskite material. In semiconductors, the refractive index is a function of wavelength, $n(\lambda)$, and by knowing the microcrystal thickness from AFM or profilometer measurements we can assign the mode index m and the refractive index $n(\lambda)$ to the reflection minima in Figure 4 (D-E). We observe a series of minima with decreasing spacing towards higher energies, because the refractive index is increasing towards the semiconductor band gap.⁴⁴ The dispersion of the refractive index for $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbBr}_4$ and PEA_2PbI_4 extracted from a series of reflectance measurements (Figure S7) on single microcrystals are reported in Figure 4F, showing the non-linear increase towards the band edge, and higher values for iodide as halide with respect to bromide, in agreement with literature.⁴⁵

When the frequency of the photonic cavity modes approaches the exciton energy, we can expect strong light-matter coupling and the formation of exciton-polaritons. Accordingly, in addition to the reflectance minima we also observe two sharp dips in reflectance near the exciton energy

(highlighted by the vertical dashed lines in Figure 4(E-F)), which we assign to polariton modes in agreement with other reports.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹

3. Conclusion

We reported the controlled growth of regular two-dimensional perovskite microcrystals with rectangular shape and micron-size lateral dimensions, and thickness is in the range of few hundred nm to few micrometer. Single crystals with these dimensions bridge the gap between nanocrystals that are typically applied in colloidal suspension (and where the surface has a huge impact on their properties),⁵⁰ and macrocrystals with mm size that can be directly integrated in device architectures⁵¹ for example in detectors.⁵² So far, low-dimensional perovskites within the micron size range were available as powders, grains in thin films, or as exfoliated flakes. The high crystalline quality of the microcrystals in our work opens opportunities for their implementation as pixels in optoelectronic devices, and their high refractive index and optical cavity properties are especially appealing for applications in photonics. We previously reported that their optical emission is highly directional with respect to the crystal lattice orientation, which could be exploited by oriented assembly of such microcrystals in arrays. The high purity and refractive index render them optimal materials for light confinement, which is paired with their light emission and tunable band gap in the visible spectral range. This combination leads to polaritonic behavior,⁴⁴ and these microcrystals can be an ideal platform for strong light-matter interaction and related photonic applications.

These properties are also very attractive for basic research and understanding of the photo-physics of low-dimensional metal halide perovskites. Here, the excellent shape and good size control can be used to reveal structure-function relations, including intrinsic polarization,^{11, 38} and the impact of edges, surfaces, and defects.

Finally, the fabrication approach that we demonstrated for 2D perovskites could possibly be applied to other emerging materials allowing to obtain high quality microcrystals.

4. Experimental Section/Methods

Chemicals and Reagents

Lead(II) bromide (PbBr_2 , $\geq 98\%$), lead(II) iodide (PbI_2 , 99%), manganese(II) bromide (MnBr_2 , 98%), hydrobromic acid (HBr, 48%), hydroiodic acid (HI, 57%, distilled, 99.999% trace metal basis), hypophosphorous acid (H_3PO_2 , 50%), phenethylamine (PEA, 99%), Butylamine (BA, 99.5%), 4-Fluorophenethylamine (FPEA, 99%), acetone ($\geq 99.5\%$), ethyl acetate

($\geq 99.5\%$), N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.8 %, anhydrous), toluene ($\geq 99.7\%$, anhydrous), 2-propanol (IPA, ACS reagent, $\geq 99.5\%$), acetonitrile (ACN, anhydrous, 99.8 %), chlorobenzene (CB, anhydrous, 99.8 %) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich without any further purification.

Synthesis of 2DLP Microcrystalline Powders

2DLP powders were prepared following a previously reported method with slight modifications.²² In brief for Br-based powders, 0.25 mmol of PbBr_2 was dissolved in 200 μL of HBr, followed by 2 mL of acetone. Subsequently, 0.6 mmol of the respective amine was injected into the solution, resulting in the immediate precipitation of 2DLP powder. The mixture was continuously agitated for at least 3 h to ensure a complete reaction. The powder was then separated by centrifugation at 6000 rpm for 2 min, redispersed in 2 mL of acetone, and washed two more times using the same procedure. The purified powder was dried under vacuum for 1 hour. The synthesis of I-based 2DLPs followed the same procedure, with PbBr_2 and HBr replaced by PbI_2 and HI, respectively. Ethyl acetate was used as the antisolvent to account for the higher solubility of I-based 2DLPs in acetone.

Growth of 2DLP MC on Substrates

The preparation of the stock solutions as well as the microcrystal growth were typically performed in an N_2 -filled glove box. For the growth of Br-based 2DLP microcrystals a stock solution of the corresponding powder where prepared by dissolving 0.0130 mmol of the powder in 20 ml ACN. For the synthesis of $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbBr}_4$ microcrystals, 2 mL of the stock solution was transferred into a vial and mixed with toluene. To obtain microcrystals with average edge length of 20 μm , the 2 mL of stock solution were mixed with 1.3 mL of toluene ($R=0.65$). The resulting cloudy mixture was heated to 55°C. Once the solution turned clear, 50 μL were drop-cast onto a 1×1 cm substrate, which was placed in a Petri dish (diameter of 3 cm) on a hot plate set to maintain the substrate temperature at 25 °C. The petri dish was covered to ensure slow and complete evaporation of the solvent system (1-2 h), resulting in the formation of well-defined $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbBr}_4$ microcrystals.

For a typical growth of PEA_2PbI_4 microcrystals, 0.0105 mmol of the precursor powder was dissolved in 1 mL of acetonitrile (ACN). Then, 100 μL of this stock solution was transferred to a separate vial and diluted with 450 μL ACN, 450 μL isopropanol (IPA), and 5 μL dimethylformamide (DMF). To adjust the saturation of the solution, 2.5 mL of chlorobenzene

(CB) was added. Finally, 45 μL of the resulting mixture was drop-cast onto a 1×1 cm substrate placed in a covered 3 cm-diameter Petri dish on a hot plate set to 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, allowing the solvent mixture to evaporate slowly.

For Mn-doped $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbBr}_4$ microcrystals, a stock solution of MnBr was prepared by dissolving 0.130 mmol of powder in 20 ml of ACN. Subsequently 100 μL are added to the 2mL $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbBr}_4$ stock solution and mixed together with 1.3 mL of toluene. The mixture was heated to 55 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Once the solution turned clear, 50 μL were drop-cast onto a 1×1 cm SiO_2 substrate, which was placed in a Petri dish (diameter of 3 cm) on a hot plate set to maintain the substrate temperature at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Lateral size and height evaluation

To determine the lateral size distribution optical micrographs of the whole substrate were collected with an optical profilometer Zeta-20 with a 10x or 20x objective. For the evaluation of the lateral size image sequences in the x- and y-direction were collected. A pixel classification model was trained in Ilastik using a representative set of optical microscopy images from our samples. Once trained, this model was applied in batch mode to process images acquired along the x- and y-directions, generating pixel classification maps that effectively distinguish microcrystals from the substrate. These maps were then analyzed using a custom Python script. Each image was first normalized and converted to an 8-bit greyscale, and external contours were extracted. A minimum threshold area of 64 pixels was set to exclude noise and very small features. For each valid contour, a rotated rectangle was fitted. The fit quality was assessed by comparing the contour area to the area of the fitted rectangle; rectangles where this ratio exceeded 0.75 were considered well-fitted and retained for further analysis. The pixel dimensions were converted to micrometers using calibration factors determined for each magnification setting.

Height evaluation: To measure a large number of microcrystals on short time scales, a Dektak profilometer was employed. For the height statistic, 5 line scans of each 5 mm length were performed on each sample, with a scan duration of 120 seconds.

Optical Characterization

Photoluminescence (PL) spectra were recorded using an Edinburgh Instruments FLS920 fluorescence spectrometer, which is equipped with a Xenon lamp and monochromator for steady-state excitation. Photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) measurements were

performed using an integrating sphere attached to the same system, by exciting the sample at 370 nm. Time-resolved PL was measured using a time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) unit in combination with a pulsed diode laser. Samples were excited at 372 nm with 50 ps pulses at a 2 μ s repetition rate. Confocal PL images were acquired using a Nikon A1R+/A1+ confocal laser scanning microscope, equipped with either a 20 \times air objective (NA 0.6) or a 60 \times oil immersion objective. Excitation was provided by a 400 nm laser, and PL was collected between 415 nm and 600 nm with a spectral resolution of 6 nm. Reflectance and photoluminescence (PL) measurements on single microcrystals were performed using a home-built setup equipped with in situ imaging capabilities. For aberration-free optical reflectance measurements, a collimated beam from a broadband light source (AvaLight-DH-S, Avantes) was focused onto the sample using a 40 \times reflective objective (Thorlabs) with a numerical aperture of 0.5. The same objective was used to collect the reflected light, which was guided to a fiber-coupled spectrometer (AvaSpec2048, Avantes). Reflectance spectra were normalized using a reference signal obtained from a high-reflectivity silver mirror (Thorlabs). The setup was also configured for PL measurements by integrating a 350 nm nanosecond pulsed laser (Spectra Physics) as the excitation source, which was focused through a 40 \times objective (Olympus). The PL was collected along the same optical path and directed to the same spectrometer. The sample was mounted on an x - y - z micro-positioning stage, enabling precise spatial scanning. Additionally, a camera (Thorlabs) integrated into the optical path provided *in-situ* imaging of the sample surface, enabling real-time positioning and quality of the crystals and accurate alignment of the measurement region.

X-ray Diffraction

The microcrystalline powders were pressed on a glass slide and placed on a zero-diffraction silicon substrate for the measurements. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded under ambient conditions using a parallel beam geometry and in symmetric reflection mode with a PANalytical Empyrean X-ray diffractometer with a 1.8 kW CuK α ceramic X-ray tube and a PIXcel3D 2 \times 2 area detector, operating at 45 kV and 40 mA.

Atomic Force Microscopy

AFM images and topological analysis of the microcrystals were performed using an XE-100 AFM system (Park Scientific), operating in a non-contact mode. The samples for the AFM imaging were prepared on microcrystals grown on Silicon Oxide.

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Data Availability Statement

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Table of contents entry

A simple and scalable method to fabricate two-dimensional layered metal halide microcrystals with rectangular shape, extremely flat surfaces, and submicron thickness is presented. The growth occurs in evaporating droplets on planar substrates, which enables the fabrication of the microcrystals directly on functional surfaces. The microcrystals demonstrate excellent optical properties in terms of refractive index, color purity, and emission wavelength tunability.

Direct Growth of Rectangular 2D Layered Metal-Halide Perovskite Microcrystal Photonic Cavities on Functional Substrates

ToC figure

